

A standardized framework for risk-based assessment of treatment effect heterogeneity in observational healthcare databases

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Abstract (247 words)

Aim: One of the aims of the Observation Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) initiative is population-level treatment effect estimation in large observational databases. Since treatment effects are well-known to vary across groups of patients with different baseline risk, we aimed to extend the OHDSI methods library with a framework for risk-based assessment of treatment effect heterogeneity.

Materials and Methods: The proposed framework consists of five steps: 1) definition of the problem, i.e. the population, the treatment, the comparator and the outcome(s) of interest; 2) identification of relevant databases; 3) development of a prediction model for the outcome(s) of interest; 4) estimation of propensity scores within strata of predicted risk and estimation of relative and absolute treatment effect within strata of predicted risk; 5) evaluation and presentation of results.

Results: We demonstrate our framework by evaluating heterogeneity of the effect of angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors versus beta blockers on a set of 9 outcomes of interest across three observational databases. With increasing risk of acute myocardial infarction we observed increasing absolute benefits, i.e. from -0.03% to 0.54% in the lowest to highest risk groups. Cough-related absolute harms decreased from 4.1% to 2.6%.

Conclusions: The proposed framework may be useful for the evaluation of heterogeneity of treatment effect on observational data that are mapped to the OMOP Common Data Model. The proof of concept study demonstrates its feasibility in large observational data. Further insights may arise by application to safety and effectiveness questions across the global data network.

Introduction

Interest in understanding how a treatment's effect varies across patients—a concept described as heterogeneity of treatment effects (HTE)—has been growing. This concept is central to the agenda for both personalized (or precision) medicine and comparative effectiveness research. More formally, HTE has been defined as non-random variability in the direction or magnitude of a treatment effect, in which the effect is measured using clinical outcomes [1]. The scale on which treatment effect is evaluated is very relevant [2]. Usually, analyses focus on the relative scale, where treatment effects are assessed one at a time in patient subgroups defined from single covariates, an approach that suffers from low power and multiplicity issues. However, even with well-established constant relative effects, treatment benefit (or harm) may vary substantially on the absolute scale.

More recently, “predictive” HTE analyses have been described (and contrasted with “one-variable-at-a-time” subgroup analysis) as approaches that provide predictions of potential outcomes in a particular patient with one intervention versus an alternative, taking into account multiple relevant patient characteristics. One promising approach is “risk modeling”, in which treatment effects are estimated in strata of predicted risk [3,4]. Such a risk-based approach first stratifies patients according to baseline risk predictions, using either an existing or an internally developed risk prediction model [3]. Then, relative and absolute treatment effects are estimated within risk strata.

While these approaches have generally been recommended for application to clinical trials, observational databases are also an appealing substrate. Observational healthcare databases, such as administrative claims and electronic health records, are already highly available for the analysis of pharmacoepidemiologic research questions [5,6]. They are also often larger than many typical trials, providing excellent power for HTE analysis, and include heterogeneous populations. However, unlike

trials, treatment effects are subject to confounding and the unique structure of different databases calls for database-specific analysis plans that are often not easily transportable.

The Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) collaborative [7] has established an international network of data partners and researchers that aim to bring out the value of health data through large-scale analytics by mapping all available databases to the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM) [8]. The common data structure enables analyses at a very large scale. For example, in a recent study [9], a large set of first-line treatments for hypertension was compared with respect to 55 outcomes in a network of databases, including 4.9 million patients from around the world.

We aimed to develop a framework for risk-based assessment of treatment effect heterogeneity in high-dimensional observational data. We implemented the framework using existing OHDSI methods for use in the OMOP-CDM, including the patient-level prediction framework [10] and the population-level effect estimation framework based on new-user cohort design [11]. As a proof-of-concept we analyzed heterogeneity of the effects of first-line hypertension treatment: we compared the effect of angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors to beta blockers on 9 outcomes across three different US claims databases.

Methods

The proposed framework defines 5 distinct steps that enable a standardized approach for risk-based assessment of treatment effect heterogeneity for databases mapped to the OMOP-CDM. These are: 1) general definition of the research aim; 2) identification of the database within which the analyses will be performed; 3) a prediction step where internal or external prediction models are used to assign patient-

level risk predictions; 4) an estimation step where absolute and relative treatment effects are estimated within risk strata; 5) presentation and evaluation of the results. A simple overview of the procedure can be seen in Figure 1.

Step 1: General definition of the problem

The typical research aim is: "to compare the effect of treatment T to a comparator treatment C in patients with disease D with respect to outcomes O_1, \dots, O_n ". At least three cohorts are defined:

- A single **treatment cohort** (T) which includes patients with disease D receiving the target treatment of interest. For example, a set of hypertension patients within a database that receive angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, followed from the time of initiation until the time of censoring.
- A single **comparator cohort** (C) which includes patients with disease D receiving the comparator (control) treatment. For example, a set of patients in a database that receive beta blockers, followed from the time of initiation until the time of censoring.
- One or more **outcome cohorts** (O_1, \dots, O_n) that contain patients developing the outcomes of interest. For example, the set of patients in a database that have at least one occurrence of hospitalization with heart failure in their record.

Step 2: Identification of the database

The aim of this step is the inclusion of databases that represent the patient population of interest. The inclusion of multiple databases potentially increases the generalizability of results. Furthermore, the

cohorts should preferably have adequate sample size to ensure precise effect estimation, even within smaller risk strata.

Step 3: Prediction

We adopt the standardized framework for the generation of patient-level prediction models using observational data [8] that ensures adherence to existing guidelines [12,13]. This prediction framework requires the definition of two essential cohorts: a target cohort and an outcome cohort. In our case, we need to ensure that our prediction model does not introduce an implicit treatment by risk interaction that may exaggerate the degree of HTE.

To generate the target cohort we pool the already defined treatment cohort T and comparator cohort C . However, for risk-based analysis of treatment effects it is necessary to avoid differentially fitting the prediction model to patients across the treatment arm in order to avoid inducing spurious interactions [14,15]. To do this, we developed the patient-level prediction model in a patient sample where treatment assignment is well balanced: a propensity score matched patient subset. The propensity scores are based on LASSO logistic regression for modeling the association between treatment assignment and all available demographics, drug exposures, diagnoses, measurements and medical procedures. Finally, we need to define the time horizon for which we aim to make predictions and we need to select the machine-learning algorithm we want to use to generate patient-level predictions. Currently, the available options are regularized logistic regression, random forest, gradient boosting machines, decision tree, naive Bayes, K-nearest neighbors, neural network and deep learning (convolutional neural networks, recurrent neural network and deep nets) [16].

Step 4: Estimation

We use the patient-level prediction model to divide the target population into a set of equally-sized risk strata, typically 4 risk quarters. Then, we estimate propensity scores within risk strata. These propensity scores are used when estimating treatment effects, either by matching of patients from different treatment cohorts, by stratification of patients into groups with similar propensity scores, or by weighing patients' contribution to the estimation process. Within risk strata we estimate treatment effect both on the relative and the absolute scale. It is important to evaluate treatment effects in both scales, as—assuming a non-zero treatment effect—treatment effect cannot remain constant on both the relative and the absolute scale at the same time. Any appropriate method for the evaluation of relative and absolute treatment effects can be considered, as long as this is done consistently in all risk strata.

Step 5: Result presentation and evaluation

Our framework provides standardized output for each step of the analysis. The number of patients and person years by treatment arm along with the number of outcomes. A performance overview of the derived prediction models, including discrimination and calibration both in the propensity score matched subset, the entire population and separately for treated and comparator patients. This is rather relevant as the performance of the prediction models is directly related with our ability to single out patient subgroups where treatment may be highly beneficial or harmful. Kent et al [17] demonstrated that the event rate and the discriminative ability of the prediction model can predict very well the distribution of predicted risk. The lower the event rate and the higher the c-statistic (given good calibration) result in high risk heterogeneity, thus making estimated average treatment effects uninformative. In this case, risk stratified analysis of HTE can be more effective in singling out patient subgroups that stand to benefit (or be harmed) most by treatment in question.

Propensity score distributions by treatment group and covariate balance plots for each risk stratum. Event rates, hazard ratios and absolute risk differences in risk strata for a selected outcome, both in tables and in graphs. Hazard ratios and absolute risk differences for all analyzed outcomes by risk stratum. Finally, shiny application can be generated to enable easy sharing of the results.

Results

As a proof of concept, we focus on the comparison of angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors to beta blockers. ACE inhibitors are among the most common treatment classes for hypertension, with a well-established effectiveness. Beta blockers, even though initially widely used for the treatment of hypertension, more recent trials and meta-analyses have cast doubt on their relative effectiveness [18]. As a result, newer US guidelines do not consider them for initial treatment for hypertension [19] while in the EU guidelines combination with other antihypertensive treatments is recommended [20]. However, another meta-analysis suggested that the efficacy profile of beta blockers is similar to other major treatment classes in younger hypertensive patients [21] and, thus, countries like Canada still include them as a first-line candidate for the treatment [22].

Step 1: General definition of the problem

We demonstrate the framework with the following research aim: "to compare the effect of ACE-inhibitors (T) to the effect of beta blockers (C) in patients with established hypertension (D) with respect to 9 outcomes (O_1, \dots, O_9)". The cohorts are:

- **Treatment cohort:** Patients receiving any drug within the ACE-inhibitor class with at least one year of follow-up before treatment start and a recorded hypertension diagnosis within that year.

- **Comparator cohort:** Patients receiving any drug within the beta blocker class with at least one year of follow-up before treatment start and a recorded hypertension diagnosis within that year.
- **Outcome cohorts:** We consider 3 main and 6 safety outcome cohorts. These are patients in the database with a diagnosis of: acute myocardial infarction (MI); hospitalization with heart failure; ischemic or hemorrhagic stroke (efficacy outcomes); hypokalemia; hyperkalemia; hypotension; angioedema; cough; abnormal weight gain (safety outcomes).

All cohort definitions can be found in the supplementary material.

Step 2: Identification of the databases

We used the following databases:

- IBM MarketScan Medicare Supplemental Beneficiaries (MDCR): Represents health services of retirees (aged 65 or older) in the United States with primary or Medicare supplemental coverage through privately insured fee-for-service, point-of-service or capitated health plans. These data include adjudicated health insurance claims (e.g. inpatient, outpatient and outpatient pharmacy). Additionally, it captures laboratory tests for a subset of the covered lives.
- IBM MarketScan Medicaid (MDCD): Adjudicated US health insurance claims for Medicaid enrollees from multiple states. It includes hospital discharge diagnoses, outpatient diagnoses and procedures and outpatient pharmacy claims as well as ethnicity and Medicare eligibility.
- IBM MarketScan Commercial Claims and Encounters (CCAЕ): Data from individuals enrolled in US employer-sponsored insurance health plans. The data includes adjudicated health insurance claims (e.g. inpatient, outpatient, and outpatient pharmacy) as well as enrollment data from large

employers and health plans who provide private healthcare coverage to employees, their spouses and dependents. Additionally, it captures laboratory tests for a subset of the covered lives.

Step 3: Prediction

To obtain a target cohort for developing patient-level predictions we first merged the ACE-inhibitors cohort with the beta blockers cohort. We then matched patients in the ACE-inhibitor cohort to patients in the beta blockers cohort on the propensity score. We focused on the efficacy outcomes (acute MI, hospitalization with heart failure and hemorrhagic or ischemic stroke) for risk stratification of the patient population. In each database, for each main outcome, we developed a prediction model. We chose a time horizon of 2 years after inclusion into the target cohort. We developed the prediction models using LASSO logistic regression with 3-fold cross validation for hyper-parameter selection.

Step 4: Estimation

We used patient-level predictions to stratify the patient population into 4 risk quarters. We estimated relative and absolute treatment effects for all 9 outcomes of interest. In order to estimate risk quarter-specific treatment effects we first estimated propensity scores within risk quarters. We then used the propensity scores to stratify patients into 5 strata.

Step 5: Result presentation and evaluation

In the main manuscript we present the results of the analysis in the CCAE database with stratification based on risk predictions of acute MI. Results of analyses in the other databases and with other risk stratifications are included in the supplementary material.

For each outcome and in each risk stratum there were adequate numbers of patients (Table 1). The discriminative ability of the prediction models was moderate in the matched development subset (c-

index 0.76 for acute MI ; 0.79 for hospitalization with heart failure; 0.74 for stroke;), in the general population (c-index 0.74 for acute MI; 0.77 for hospitalization with heart failure; 0.73 for stroke), in the treatment cohort (c-index for acute MI it was 0.71, for hospitalization with heart failure was 0.76 and for stroke it was 0.72) and in the comparator cohort (c-index for acute MI it was 0.79 for hospitalization with heart failure was 0.79 and for stroke it was 0.75).

Relative treatment effects of ACE-inhibitors vs beta blockers increased (hazard ratios decreased) with increasing acute MI risk, resulting in more pronounced increases of absolute treatment effects (ARD) with increasing acute MI risk (Figure 2). Patients in the low risk quarter did not receive absolute treatment benefit (ARD -0.03%) while absolute risk was 0.54% lower (95% confidence interval 0.36%—0.71%) for patients in the high risk quarter. In contrast, the absolute and relative effects of ACE-inhibitors on safety outcomes (e.g. cough and angioedema) are approximately constant or even slightly decreasing with increasing acute MI risk (Figure 3 and 4). Similar results were observed in the other two databases (see supplementary material).

This example nicely illustrates heterogeneity of absolute treatment effects, i.e. differences in absolute benefits and harms of ACE-inhibitors vs beta blockers for patients with different baseline risk. The results suggest that treatment with ACE-inhibitors, compared to treatment with beta blockers, may be focused on the higher risk patients, in whom the benefits outweigh the harms. However, treatment with beta blockers may be a viable option in lower risk patients, in whom the benefit-harm tradeoff is in favor of beta blockers. This is in accordance with earlier findings that beta blockers should be considered as first-line treatment for younger hypertensive patients [21,23]. More thorough evaluation of these results is required in future research.

The results of the analyses performed can be accessed and assessed through a publicly available web application (<https://data.ohdsi.org/AceBeta9Outcomes>).

Discussion

We developed a framework for the assessment of heterogeneity of treatment effect in large observational databases using a risk modeling approach. The framework is implemented in an open source R-package in the OHDSI methods library (<https://github.com/OHDSI/RiskStratifiedEstimation>). As a proof-of-concept, we used our framework to evaluate heterogeneity of the effect of treatment with ACE-inhibitors compared to beta blockers on 3 efficacy and 6 safety outcomes.

In recent years several methods for the evaluation of treatment effect heterogeneity have been developed in the setting of RCTs [24]. However, low power and restricted prior knowledge on the mechanisms of variation in treatment effect are often inherent in RCTs, which are often adequately powered only for the analysis of the primary outcome. Observational databases contain a large amount of information on treatment assignment and outcomes of interest, while also capturing key patient characteristics. Our framework provides a standardized approach that can be used to leverage available information from these data sources, allowing for large-scale assessment of treatment effect heterogeneity. Multiple outcomes can be evaluated in patient subgroups of similar baseline outcome risk, where different outcome risk stratification schemes can be considered. The standardized nature of the framework enables transportability to multiple databases, provided that they are mapped to the OMOP-CDM.

Recently, guidelines on the application of risk modeling approaches for the assessment of heterogeneity of treatment effect in RCT settings have been proposed [25,26]. Our framework aims to translate these

guidelines to the observational setting while also providing a toolset for its implementation. Several considerations need to be made. First, estimates may be biased due to the observational nature of the data. We attempt to account for potential confounding by estimating propensity scores within strata of predicted risk. These scores are estimated using regularized logistic regression on a large set of pre-defined covariates. This specific approach gave accurate results in extensive simulation studies [27]. However, such approaches do not account for unobserved confounding. Several sensitivity analyses have been proposed in the literature for measuring the robustness of results in the presence of unobserved confounding [28]. Another approach is to calibrate estimates and confidence intervals based on a large set of negative controls [29,30]. Negative controls are treatment-outcome pairs for which a null effect has been established. Estimating these effects within available data provides an approximation of the null distribution that can be used to empirically recalibrate effect estimates. Future work may extend our framework with this type of analyses.

Our method provides a risk-stratified assessment of treatment effect heterogeneity. However, even though stratification can provide a rough guide for clinical interpretation, it is not appropriate to guide clinical practice, where decisions need to be made at the individual level [26]. Presentation of treatment effects as a continuous function of risk would be more helpful, but is methodologically challenging. Future research is necessary for the development of methods for continuous risk-based assessment of HTE.

Externally derived prediction models are preferred for analyzing treatment effect heterogeneity [3]. Such external models should be well transportable. In the absence of such prediction models, simulations of RCTs have shown that internally derived models can be used to provide unbiased estimates of treatment effect across the spectrum of baseline risk [15]. However, in observational databases treatment arms may significantly differ in sample size. Because the prediction model will

possibly better fit to the larger treatment arm, this may introduce spurious treatment-covariate interactions in the prediction model, leading to sub-optimal risk stratification. As a remedy, we first match the patients in the treatment and the comparator cohorts on the basis of propensity scores. Additionally, we propose to assess model performance in the separate treatment arms to evaluate its aptness for risk stratification.

Our contribution is a translation of the PATH statement principles to the OHDSI methods library. Our methods encourage open science as it requires clear definition of the research questions translated into clear and reproducible cohort definitions that can easily be shared among researchers. Our R-package provides a standardized stepwise procedure for the assessment of HTE. This enables source code to be easily shared and evaluated. The results of these analyses can be reproduced in a straightforward manner. Researchers with access to different databases mapped to OMOP-CDM can also very easily extend their overall analyses with risk-based assessment of treatment effect heterogeneity. This enables collaboration among multiple sites with access to different patient populations. We propose that the framework is implemented any time treatment effect estimation in high-dimensional observational data is undertaken.

Recently, disease risk scores have been explored as an alternative to propensity scores for balancing covariates [31–33]. In our method, the objective of risk stratification is not balancing, but assessing the variation of treatment effects on multiple outcomes across patients with different levels of baseline risk. Although using the same risk model for balancing and risk-based HTE analysis may sound attractive, we note that our method only uses one risk model for stratification and one propensity score model for balancing, while separate disease risk score models would be required to analyze treatment effects for each of the multiple outcomes.

In conclusion, the proof-of-concept study demonstrates the feasibility of our framework for risk-based assessment of treatment effect heterogeneity in large observational data. The standardized framework is easily applicable and highly informative whenever treatment effect estimation in high-dimensional observational data is of interest. Our framework is a supplement to the population-level effect estimation framework developed within OHDSI and, in the presence of an adequately discriminating prediction model, can be used to make the overall results more actionable for medical decision making.

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Tables and figures

Table 1

Outcome	Risk quarter	ACE inhibitors			Beta blockers		
		Patients	Person years	Events	Patients	Person years	Events
Acute myocardial infarction	1	161,099	276,171	203	133,977	220,633	135
	2	204,882	372,197	534	90,193	169,231	321
	3	214,413	393,583	1,117	80,662	150,035	535
	4	204,167	351,727	2,095	90,908	154,419	1,520
Heart failure (hosp)	1	146,259	249,809	228	126,387	206,706	378
	2	188,006	341,014	457	84,280	158,425	340
	3	218,052	399,394	826	83,421	155,222	570
	4	230,226	400,330	2,012	98,380	169,139	1,773
Stroke (ischemic or hemorrhagic)	1	146,069	294,484	299	126,264	206,453	320
	2	187,524	340,234	554	84,000	157,913	351
	3	217,070	397,830	947	83,038	154,587	521
	4	226,128	393,861	1,718	97,628	167,810	1,077

Table 1: Number of patients, person years and events within quarters of predicted risk for hospitalization with heart failure for the 3 main outcomes of the study (acute myocardial infarction, hospitalization with heart failure and ischemic or hemorrhagic stroke).

Table 2

Outcome	Matched	Overall	Treatment	Comparator
Acute myocardial infarction	0.76	0.74	0.71	0.79
Heart failure (hospitalization)	0.79	0.77	0.76	0.79
Stroke (ischemic or hemorrhagic)	0.74	0.73	0.72	0.75

Table 2: Area under the ROC curve of the prediction models developed within CCAE on the propensity score matched population. The performance on the development (matched) subset is given in first column, in second column the performance of the model in the entire population is provided. Columns 3 and 4 provide the performance in separate treatment arms.

Figure 1

Figure 1: (A) Starting from a treatment (top), a comparator (bottom) and an outcome (middle) cohort we estimate the propensity scores on the entire target population. (B) We match patients on the propensity scores and estimate the prediction model. Since we match patients we develop the prediction model on smaller subset of the initial population and, therefore, the number of patients is smaller in B compared to A. (C) We apply the prediction model on the entire population (green: lower 25% of the risk distribution; yellow: patients with risk between 25% and 50% of the risk distribution; orange: patients with risk between 50% and 75% of the risk distribution; red: patients at risk higher than 75% of the risk distribution). (D) We separate in risk subgroups, here quarters. Within risk quarters propensity scores are estimated again and relative and absolute treatment effects are estimated.

Figure 2

Figure 2: Overview of heterogeneity of ACE-inhibitors treatment within strata of predicted risk of acute MI. The top panel contains the observed acute rates of ACE-inhibitors and beta blockers within each quarter of predicted acute MI risk. These are derived using the Kaplan-Meier estimates at 730 days after inclusion. The middle panel, contains the hazard ratios of comparing ACE-inhibitors to beta blockers with regard to acute MI. These are estimated using Cox proportional hazards regression within quarters of predicted acute MI risk. The bottom panel contains absolute risk reduction for ACE-inhibitors compared to beta blockers. These are derived as the difference in Kaplan-Meier estimates at 730 after inclusion. Hazard ratios in the middle panel show a decreasing trend with increasing acute MI risk. Given the rather good discrimination of the prediction model (AUC=0.74), this results in an increasing trend for absolute benefit in favor of ACE-inhibitors with increasing risk.

Figure 3

Figure 3: Hazard ratios (relative treatment effects) for the main and safety outcomes, estimated by fitting stratified cox regression models within quarters of predicted risk of acute myocardial infarction. The four risk quarters (Q1-Q4) are defined using the internally developed model for acute MI.

Figure 4

Figure 4: Absolute risk reduction for the main and safety outcomes, estimated as the difference in Kaplan-Meier estimates within quarters of predicted risk for acute MI. The four risk quarters (Q1-Q4) are defined using the internally developed model for acute MI.

Supplementary material

Cohort definitions

Treatment cohorts

First-line new user ACE inhibitors

Initial Event Cohort

People having any of the following:

- a drug exposure of [LEGEND HTN] ACE inhibitors²
 - ◆ for the first time in the person's history

with continuous observation of at least 365 days prior and 0 days after event index date, and limit initial events to: earliest event per person.

For people matching the Primary Events, include:

Having all of the following criteria:

- exactly 0 occurrences of a drug exposure of [LEGEND HTN] Hypertension drugs⁴ where event starts between all days Before and 1 days Before index start date
- and at least 1 occurrences of a condition occurrence of Hypertensive disorder¹ where event starts between 365 days Before and 0 days After index start date
- and exactly 1 distinct occurrences of a drug era of [LEGEND HTN] Hypertension drugs⁴ where event starts between 0 days Before and 7 days After index start date

Limit cohort of initial events to: earliest event per person.

Limit qualifying cohort to: earliest event per person.

End Date Strategy

Custom Drug Era Exit Criteria

This strategy creates a drug era from the codes found in the specified concept set. If the index event is found within an era, the cohort end date will use the era's end date. Otherwise, it will use the observation period end date that contains the index event.

Use the era end date of [LEGEND HTN] ACE inhibitors2

- allowing 30 days between exposures
- adding 0 days after exposure end
- using days supply and exposure end date for exposure duration.

Cohort Collapse Strategy:

Collapse cohort by era with a gap size of 0 days.

Concept Set Definitions

1. Hypertensive disorder

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
316866	Hypertensive disorder	Condition	SNOMED	NO	YES	NO

2. ACE inhibitors

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
1308216	Lisinopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO

1310756	moexipril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1331235	quinapril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1334456	Ramipril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1335471	benazepril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1340128	Captopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1341927	Enalapril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1342439	trandolapril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1363749	Fosinopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1373225	Perindopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO

3. First-line hypertension drugs

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
907013	Metolazone	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
974166	Hydrochlorothiazide	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
978555	Indapamide	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1307863	Verapamil	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1308216	Lisinopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1308842	valsartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1310756	moexipril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1317640	telmisartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1318137	Nicardipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1318853	Nifedipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1319880	Nisoldipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1326012	Isradipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1328165	Diltiazem	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1331235	quinapril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1332418	Amlodipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1334456	Ramipril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1335471	benazepril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1340128	Captopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1341927	Enalapril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1342439	trandolapril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1346686	eprosartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1347384	irbesartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1351557	candesartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1353776	Felodipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1363749	Fosinopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1367500	Losartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1373225	Perindopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1395058	Chlorthalidone	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
40226742	olmesartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO

40235485	azilsartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
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4. Hypertension drugs

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
40235485	azilsartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
40226742	olmesartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1398937	Clonidine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1395058	Chlorthalidone	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1386957	Labetalol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1373928	Hydralazine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1373225	Perindopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1367500	Losartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1363749	Fosinopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1363053	Doxazosin	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1353776	Felodipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1353766	Propranolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1351557	candesartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1350489	Prazosin	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1347384	irbesartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1346823	carvedilol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1346686	eprosartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1345858	Pindolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1344965	Guanfacine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1342439	trandolapril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1341927	Enalapril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1341238	Terazosin	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1340128	Captopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1338005	Bisoprolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1335471	benazepril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1334456	Ramipril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1332418	Amlodipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1331235	quinapril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1328165	Diltiazem	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1327978	Penbutolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1326012	Isradipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1322081	Betaxolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1319998	Acebutolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1319880	Nisoldipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1318853	Nifedipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1318137	Nicardipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1317967	aliskiren	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO

1317640	telmisartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1314577	nebivolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1314002	Atenolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1313200	Nadolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1310756	moexipril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1309799	eplerenone	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1309068	Minoxidil	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1308842	valsartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1308216	Lisinopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1307863	Verapamil	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1307046	Metoprolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1305447	Methyldopa	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
991382	Amiloride	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
978555	Indapamide	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
974166	Hydrochlorothiazide	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
970250	Spirolactone	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
956874	Furosemide	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
942350	torseamide	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
932745	Bumetanide	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
907013	Metolazone	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
904542	Triamterene	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO

First-line new user beta blockers

Initial Event Cohort

People having any of the following:

- a drug exposure of Beta blockers(see 2 below)
 - ◆ for the first time in the person's history

with continuous observation of at least 365 days prior and 0 days after event index date, and limit initial events to: earliest event per person.

For people matching the Primary Events, include:

Having all of the following criteria:

- exactly 0 occurrences of a drug exposure of Hypertension drugs (see 4 below) where event starts between all days Before and 1 days Before index start date
- and at least 1 occurrences of a condition occurrence of Hypertensive disorder (see 1 below) where event starts between 365 days Before and 0 days After index start date
- and exactly 1 distinct occurrences of a drug era of Hypertension drugs (see 4 below) where event starts between 0 days Before and 7 days After index start date

Limit cohort of initial events to: earliest event per person.

Limit qualifying cohort to: earliest event per person.

End Date Strategy

[Custom Drug Era Exit Criteria](#)

This strategy creates a drug era from the codes found in the specified concept set. If the index event is found within an era, the cohort end date will use the era's end date. Otherwise, it will use the observation period end date that contains the index event.

Use the era end date of Beta blockers (see 2 below)

- allowing 30 days between exposures
- adding 0 days after exposure end

[Cohort Collapse Strategy:](#)

Collapse cohort by era with a gap size of 0 days.

Concept Set Definitions

1. Hypertensive disorder

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
316866	Hypertensive disorder	Condition	SNOMED	NO	YES	NO

2. Beta blockers

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
1307046	Metoprolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1313200	Nadolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1314002	Atenolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1314577	nebivolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1319998	Acebutolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1322081	Betaxolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1327978	Penbutolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1338005	Bisoprolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1345858	Pindolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1346823	carvedilol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1353766	Propranolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1386957	Labetalol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO

3. First-line hypertension drugs

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
907013	Metolazone	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
974166	Hydrochlorothiazide	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
978555	Indapamide	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1307863	Verapamil	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1308216	Lisinopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1308842	valsartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1310756	moexipril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1317640	telmisartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1318137	Nicardipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1318853	Nifedipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1319880	Nisoldipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1326012	Isradipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1328165	Diltiazem	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1331235	quinapril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO

1332418	Amlodipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1334456	Ramipril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1335471	benazepril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1340128	Captopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1341927	Enalapril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1342439	trandolapril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1346686	eprosartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1347384	irbesartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1351557	candesartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1353776	Felodipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1363749	Fosinopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1367500	Losartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1373225	Perindopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1395058	Chlorthalidone	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
40226742	olmesartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
40235485	azilsartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO

4. Hypertension drugs

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
904542	Triamterene	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
907013	Metolazone	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
932745	Bumetanide	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
942350	torseamide	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
956874	Furosemide	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
970250	Spironolactone	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
974166	Hydrochlorothiazide	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
978555	Indapamide	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
991382	Amiloride	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1305447	Methyldopa	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1307046	Metoprolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1307863	Verapamil	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1308216	Lisinopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1308842	valsartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1309068	Minoxidil	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1309799	eplerenone	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1310756	moexipril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1313200	Nadolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1314002	Atenolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1314577	nebivolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1317640	telmisartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1317967	aliskiren	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO

1318137	Nicardipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1318853	Nifedipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1319880	Nisoldipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1319998	Acebutolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1322081	Betaxolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1326012	Isradipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1327978	Penbutolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1328165	Diltiazem	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1331235	quinapril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1332418	Amlodipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1334456	Ramipril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1335471	benazepril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1338005	Bisoprolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1340128	Captopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1341238	Terazosin	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1341927	Enalapril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1342439	trandolapril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1344965	Guanfacine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1345858	Pindolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1346686	eprosartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1346823	carvedilol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1347384	irbesartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1350489	Prazosin	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1351557	candesartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1353766	Propranolol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1353776	Felodipine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1363053	Doxazosin	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1363749	Fosinopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1367500	Losartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1373225	Perindopril	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1373928	Hydralazine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1386957	Labetalol	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1395058	Chlorthalidone	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
1398937	Clonidine	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
40226742	olmesartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO
40235485	azilsartan	Drug	RxNorm	NO	YES	NO

Outcome cohorts

Hospitalization with heart failure

Inpatient or ER visits with heart failure condition record; all qualifying inpatient visits occurring > 7 days apart are considered independent episodes

Initial Event Cohort

People having any of the following:

- a visit occurrence of Inpatient or ER visit (see 1 below) having one of the following:
 - ◆ at least 1 occurrences of a condition occurrence of Heart Failure (see 2 below) where event starts between 0 days Before and all days After index start date and event starts between all days Before and 0 days After index end date

with continuous observation of at least 0 days prior and 0 days after event index date, and limit initial events to: all events per person.

Limit qualifying cohort to: all events per person.

End Date Strategy

[Date Offset Exit Criteria](#)

This cohort definition end date will be the index event's end date plus 0 days

[Cohort Collapse Strategy:](#)

Collapse cohort by era with a gap size of 7 days.

Concept Set Definitions

1. Inpatient or ER visit

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
262	Emergency Room and Inpatient Visit	Visit	Visit	NO	YES	NO
9201	Inpatient Visit	Visit	Visit	NO	YES	NO
9203	Emergency Room Visit	Visit	Visit	NO	YES	NO

2. Heart Failure

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
315295	Congestive rheumatic heart failure	Condition	SNOMED	YES	YES	NO
316139	Heart failure	Condition	SNOMED	NO	YES	NO

Acute Myocardial Infarction

Initial Event Cohort

People having any of the following:

- a condition occurrence of [LEGEND HTN] Acute myocardial Infarction (see 2 below)

with continuous observation of at least 0 days prior and 0 days after event index date, and limit initial events to: all events per person.

For people matching the Primary Events, include:

Having any of the following criteria:

- at least 1 occurrences of a visit occurrence of Inpatient or ER visit (see 1 below) where event starts between all days Before and 0 days After index start date and event ends between 0 days Before and all days After index start date

Limit cohort of initial events to: all events per person.

Limit qualifying cohort to: all events per person.

End Date Strategy

[Date Offset Exit Criteria](#)

This cohort definition end date will be the index event's start date plus 7 days

[Cohort Collapse Strategy:](#)

Collapse cohort by era with a gap size of 180 days.

Concept Set Definitions

1. Inpatient or ER visit

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
262	Emergency Room and Inpatient Visit	Visit	Visit	NO	YES	NO
9201	Inpatient Visit	Visit	Visit	NO	YES	NO
9203	Emergency Room Visit	Visit	Visit	NO	YES	NO

2. Acute myocardial Infarction

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
314666	Old myocardial infarction	Condition	SNOMED	YES	YES	NO

4329847	Myocardial infarction	Condition	SNOMED	NO	YES	NO
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Stroke (ischemic or hemorrhagic) events

Stroke (ischemic or hemorrhagic) condition record during an inpatient or ER visit; successive records with > 180 day gap are considered independent episodes

Initial Event Cohort

People having any of the following:

- a condition occurrence of Stroke ischemic or hemorrhagic (see 2 below)

with continuous observation of at least 0 days prior and 0 days after event index date, and limit initial events to: all events per person.

For people matching the Primary Events, include:

Having any of the following criteria:

- at least 1 occurrences of a visit occurrence of Inpatient or ER visit (see 1 below)

where event starts between all days Before and 1 days After index start date and event ends between 0 days Before and all days After index start date

Limit cohort of initial events to: all events per person.

Limit qualifying cohort to: all events per person.

End Date Strategy

[Date Offset Exit Criteria](#)

This cohort definition end date will be the index event's start date plus 7 days

[Cohort Collapse Strategy:](#)

Collapse cohort by era with a gap size of 180 days.

Concept Set Definitions

1. Inpatient or ER visit

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
262	Emergency Room and Inpatient Visit	Visit	Visit	NO	YES	NO
9201	Inpatient Visit	Visit	Visit	NO	YES	NO
9203	Emergency Room Visit	Visit	Visit	NO	YES	NO

2. Stroke (ischemic or hemorrhagic)

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
372924	Cerebral artery occlusion	Condition	SNOMED	NO	NO	NO
375557	Cerebral embolism	Condition	SNOMED	NO	NO	NO
376713	Cerebral hemorrhage	Condition	SNOMED	NO	NO	NO
432923	Subarachnoid hemorrhage	Condition	SNOMED	NO	NO	NO
439847	Intracranial hemorrhage	Condition	SNOMED	NO	NO	NO
441874	Cerebral thrombosis	Condition	SNOMED	NO	NO	NO
443454	Cerebral infarction	Condition	SNOMED	NO	YES	NO

Abnormal weight gain events

Abnormal weight gain record of any type; successive records with > 90 day gap are considered independent episodes

Initial Event Cohort

People having any of the following:

- an observation of [LEGEND HTN] Abnormal weight gain (see 1 below)

with continuous observation of at least 0 days prior and 0 days after event index date, and limit initial events to: all events per person.

Limit qualifying cohort to: all events per person.

End Date Strategy

[Date Offset Exit Criteria](#)

This cohort definition end date will be the index event's start date plus 1 days

[Cohort Collapse Strategy:](#)

Collapse cohort by era with a gap size of 90 days.

Concept Set Definitions

1. Abnormal weight gain

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
439141	Abnormal weight gain	Observation	SNOMED	NO	YES	NO

Angioedema events

Angioedema condition record during an inpatient or ER visit; successive records with >7 day gap are considered independent episodes

Initial Event Cohort

People having any of the following:

- a condition occurrence of [LEGEND HTN] Angioedema (see 2 below)

with continuous observation of at least 0 days prior and 0 days after event index date, and limit initial events to: all events per person.

For people matching the Primary Events, include:

Having any of the following criteria:

- at least 1 occurrences of a visit occurrence of Inpatient or ER visit (see 1 below)

where event starts between all days Before and 0 days After index start date and event ends between 0 days Before and all days After index start date

Limit cohort of initial events to: all events per person.

Limit qualifying cohort to: all events per person.

End Date Strategy

[Date Offset Exit Criteria](#)

This cohort definition end date will be the index event's start date plus 7 days

[Cohort Collapse Strategy:](#)

Collapse cohort by era with a gap size of 30 days.

Concept Set Definitions

1. Inpatient or ER visit

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
262	Emergency Room and Inpatient Visit	Visit	Visit	NO	YES	NO
9201	Inpatient Visit	Visit	Visit	NO	YES	NO
9203	Emergency Room Visit	Visit	Visit	NO	YES	NO

2. Angioedema

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
432791	Angioedema	Condition	SNOMED	NO	YES	NO

Cough events

Cough condition record of any type; successive records with > 90 day gap are considered independent episodes

Initial Event Cohort

People having any of the following:

- a condition occurrence of [LEGEND HTN] Cough (see 1 below)

with continuous observation of at least 0 days prior and 0 days after event index date, and limit initial events to: all events per person.

Limit qualifying cohort to: all events per person.

End Date Strategy

[Date Offset Exit Criteria](#)

This cohort definition end date will be the index event's start date plus 1 days

[Cohort Collapse Strategy:](#)

Collapse cohort by era with a gap size of 90 days.

Concept Set Definitions

1. Cough

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
254761	Cough	Condition	SNOMED	NO	YES	NO

Hyperkalemia events

Condition record for hyperkalemia or potassium measurements > 5.6 mmol/L; successive records with >90 day gap are considered independent episodes

Initial Event Cohort

People having any of the following:

- a condition occurrence of [LEGEND HTN] Hyperkalemia (see 1 below)
- a measurement of [LEGEND HTN] Potassium measurement (see 2 below)
 - ◆ with value as number > 5.6
 - ◆ unit is any of: millimole per liter

with continuous observation of at least 0 days prior and 0 days after event index date, and limit initial events to: all events per person.

Limit qualifying cohort to: all events per person.

End Date Strategy

[Date Offset Exit Criteria](#)

This cohort definition end date will be the index event's start date plus 1 days

[Cohort Collapse Strategy:](#)

Collapse cohort by era with a gap size of 90 days.

Concept Set Definitions

1. Hyperkalemia

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
434610	Hyperkalemia	Condition	SNOMED	NO	YES	NO

2. Potassium measurement

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
4245152	Potassium measurement	Measurement	SNOMED	NO	YES	NO
4276440	Potassium level - finding	Condition	SNOMED	NO	YES	NO
40789893	Potassium Bld-Ser-Plas	Measurement	LOINC	NO	YES	NO

Hypokalemia events

Hypokalemia condition record of any type; successive records with > 90 day gap are considered independent episodes

Initial Event Cohort

People having any of the following:

- a condition occurrence of Hypokalemia (see 1 below)

with continuous observation of at least 0 days prior and 0 days after event index date, and limit initial events to: all events per person.

Limit qualifying cohort to: all events per person.

End Date Strategy

[Date Offset Exit Criteria](#)

This cohort definition end date will be the index event's start date plus 1 days

[Cohort Collapse Strategy:](#)

Collapse cohort by era with a gap size of 90 days.

Concept Set Definitions

1. Hypokalemia

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
437833	Hypokalemia	Condition	SNOMED	NO	YES	NO
45769152	Bartter syndrome	Condition	SNOMED	YES	YES	NO

Hypotension events

Hypotension condition record of any type; successive records with > 90 day gap are considered independent episodes

Initial Event Cohort

People having any of the following:

- a condition occurrence of [LEGEND HTN] Hypotension (see 1 below)

with continuous observation of at least 0 days prior and 0 days after event index date, and limit initial events to: all events per person.

Limit qualifying cohort to: all events per person.

End Date Strategy

[Date Offset Exit Criteria](#)

This cohort definition end date will be the index event's start date plus 1 days

Cohort Collapse Strategy:

Collapse cohort by era with a gap size of 90 days.

Concept Set Definitions

1. Hypotension

Concept Id	Concept Name	Domain	Vocabulary	Excluded	Descendants	Mapped
313232	Hemodialysis-associated hypotension	Observation	SNOMED	YES	YES	NO
314432	Maternal hypotension syndrome	Condition	SNOMED	YES	YES	NO
317002	Low blood pressure	Condition	SNOMED	NO	YES	NO

Results

CCAЕ

Covariate balance

Figure S1: Standardized mean difference of the covariates before and after PS-stratification in all risk strata. Here we present only the analysis where we stratify in quarters of predicted acute myocardial infarction risk and assess heterogeneity of treatment effect with respect to the same outcome.

Propensity scores

Figure S2: Distribution of propensity scores in all risk strata. Here we present only the analysis where we stratify in quarters of predicted acute myocardial infarction risk and assess heterogeneity of treatment effect with respect to the same outcome.

Prediction

Discrimination

Figure S3: ROC curve of the model predicting acute myocardial infarction based on the propensity score-matched sub-population.

Figure S4: ROC curve of the model predicting acute myocardial infarction based on the entire population.

Figure S5: ROC curve of the model predicting acute myocardial infarction based on the treatment arm.

Figure S6: ROC curve of the model predicting acute myocardial infarction based on the comparator arm.

Calibration

Figure S7: Calibration plot of the model predicting acute myocardial infarction based on the propensity score-matched sub-population.

Figure S8: Calibration plot of the model predicting acute myocardial infarction based on the entire population.

Figure S9: Calibration plot of the model predicting acute myocardial infarction based on the treatment arm.

Figure S10: Calibration plot of the model predicting acute myocardial infarction based on the comparator arm.

MDCD

Outcome	Risk quarter	ACE inhibitors			Beta blockers		
		Patients	Person years	Events	Patients	Person years	Events
Acute myocardial infarction	1	14,347	19,972	15	13,858	17,056	20
	2	18,412	26,737	99	9,793	14,180	53
	3	18,893	31,231	226	9,312	15,041	174
	4	15,168	27,383	561	13,036	22,158	587
Heart failure (hosp)	1	18,004	25,006	87	16,028	20,042	120
	2	18,190	27,253	208	9,108	13,527	138
	3	17,386	29,261	453	8,618	14,219	340
	4	11,775	21,440	970	9,928	17,197	1,155
Stroke (ischemic or hemorrhagic)	1	17,963	24,939	59	15,996	19,991	46
	2	18,063	27,086	180	9,045	13,411	104
	3	17,129	28,846	356	8,582	14,155	208
	4	11,917	21,627	536	10,891	18,601	573

Table S1: Number of patients, person years and events within quarters of predicted risk for acute myocardial infarction for the 3 main outcomes of the study (acute myocardial infarction, hospitalization with heart failure or haemorrhagic stroke) in MDCD.

Figure S11: Overview of heterogeneity of ACE-inhibitors treatment within strata of predicted risk of acute myocardial infarction in MDCD. The graph contains the acute myocardial infarction outcome rates in quarters of predicted risk (top), the hazard ratios (middle) and the absolute risk differences (bottom).

Figure S12: Hazard ratios for the main and safety outcomes, estimated by fitting cox regression models within quarters of predicted risk for acute myocardial infarction in MDCD. The four risk quarters (Q1-Q4) are defined using the internally developed model for acute myocardial infarction.

Figure S13: Absolute risk reduction for the main and safety outcomes, estimated as the difference in Kaplan-Meier estimates within quarters of predicted risk acute myocardial infarction in MDCD. The four risk quarters (Q1-Q4) are defined using the internally developed model for acute myocardial infarction.

MDCR

Outcome	Risk quarter	ACE inhibitors	Person years	Events	Beta blockers	Person years	Events
		Patients			Patients		
Acute myocardial infarction	1	27,853	57,541	231	15,057	32,627	142
	2	27,596	56,910	387	15,134	32,861	238
	3	25,893	53,202	560	17,017	35,187	404
	4	20,319	38,710	828	22,590	42,073	903
Heart failure (hosp)	1	27,530	56,886	364	14,847	32,183	317
	2	27,486	56,644	582	15,183	32,622	482
	3	25,482	52,475	965	16,500	34,234	865
	4	19,704	37,842	1,578	20,746	39,414	2,109
Stroke (ischemic or hemorrhagic)	1	27,291	56,413	375	14,734	31,988	229
	2	27,054	55,846	490	15,011	32,220	371
	3	24,763	50,976	752	16,209	33,763	629
	4	18,666	35,775	979	20,905	39,444	1,094

Table S2: Number of patients, person years and events within quarters of predicted risk for hospitalization with heart failure for the 3 main outcomes of the study (acute myocardial infarction, hospitalization with heart failure and ischemic or hemorrhagic stroke) in MDCR.

Figure S14: Overview of heterogeneity of ACE-inhibitors treatment within strata of predicted risk of hospitalization with heart failure in MDCR. The graph contains the acute myocardial infarction outcome rates in quarters of predicted risk (top), the hazard ratios that remain quite constant, showing no difference in relative effect with increasing risk (middle) and the absolute risk differences that remain constant close to 0 with increasing risk (bottom).

Figure S15: Hazard ratios for the main and safety outcomes, estimated by fitting cox regression models within quarters of predicted risk for hospitalization with heart failure in MDCR. The strata are defined using the internally developed model for acute myocardial infarction.

Figure S16: Absolute risk reduction for the main and safety outcomes, estimated as the difference in Kaplan-Meier estimates within quarters of predicted risk for hospitalization with heart failure in MDCR. The four risk quarters (Q1-Q4) are defined using the internally developed model for acute myocardial infarction.